

NDAC/LO/094
1987 March 5

19th NDAC Report from Lund Observatory

WP8000: Double Stars (Söderhjelm, Lindegren)

Simulation experiments concerning the reduction of double and multiple stars continued (089 = C). The treatment of double stars in the overall NDAC data processing has been reviewed (090 = C) and efforts are now concentrating on modifying the simulation package to be compatible with the proposed scheme and to implement the latter. A format for input of attitude data and instrument parameters from the Great-Circle Reduction has been proposed (093 = C).

Great-Circle Reduction (Lindegren)

A final version of the format specification for input to the Delft GCR program has been agreed on (082.1 = C). A tape with simulated data (LOSIM3.1) was sent to Delft on February 11.

Miscellaneous (Lindegren)

The observation of minor planets and natural satellites (Europa and Titan) by Hipparcos and their treatment by NDAC was reviewed (088 = C).

Standard coordinates for use in TYCHO astrometry were described in 091 = C .

A revised version of 'Conventions and Reference Systems Used by NDAC' has been issued (084.1 = C).

A method for comparing FAST and NDAC attitudes and corresponding data formats have been proposed (092 = C).

Working papers

- C Söderhjelm 1986 Dec 17: NDAC Simulations of Double and Multiple Stars (NDAC/LO/085.1) Detectability and Astrometric Accuracy (Rev.)
- C Lindegren 1986 Dec 04: ERRATUM: Specification of output for the IDT Preprocessing and Location Estimator as required for the Double Star Analysis (NDAC/LO/087)
- C Lindegren 1986 Dec 05: Hipparcos Observations of Minor Planets and Natural Satellites: NDAC Treatment and the Effects of Phase, Shape and Albedo Variation (NDAC/LO/088)
- C Söderhjelm 1986 Dec 18: HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, IVb (NDAC/LO/089)
- C Lindegren 1986 Dec 16: Treatment of Double Stars in the Overall NDAC Data Processing (NDAC/LO/090)
- C Lindegren 1986 Dec 08: Format Specification for Lund Simulated Data (NDAC/LO/082.1) Input to Delft RGC Solution (Rev. 1)
- C Lindegren 1987 Jan 12: Standard coordinates for use in TYCHO astrometry (NDAC/LO/091)
- C Lindegren 1987 Jan 29: Conventions and Reference Systems Used by NDAC (Rev. 1) (NDAC/LO/084.1)
- C Lindegren 1987 Feb 02: Proposed Format and Method of Comparison for FAST and NDAC Attitudes (NDAC/LO/092)
- C Lindegren 1987 Feb 13: Specification of Input to Step 2/3 and the Double Star Analysis from DSRI (not circulated) (NDAC/LO/093)